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The e Learning Action Plan for U.P. youth in digital age

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We are now living in the era of technology and evolution of internet has affected all part of life dramatically. Also the area of education has not remained untouched. Previously, student used to spend their time in library searching for information in books and journals. Now the required information is just a click away from them, they use web search engines such as google and figure out the web sites containing the desired information. The information sharing has become very easy due to access on World Wide Web (www) as the world persons and their knowledge attach to each other by a web and can be transferred to each other.

The impact of internet on education is that teaching, education and learning all have a common purpose, i.e., to impart knowledge to their subjects to enable them to do certain tasks. Elaborating further, learning is done by subjects and the process involves cognitive abilities of subject, which leads to learning via experience via all the senses. Teaching is the effort done by teacher. The system where teaching and learning both happen in a harmonious fashion is education. Consequently, education is a paradigm. Teaching in essence creates an environment which leads to learning experience for the student. The ability of teacher lies in the fact that he can create an environment which leads to a certain desired experience for the student.

In the present traditional system of our education, the teacher takes the feedback by evaluating the students through examination or by the questions asked by the students, *it consists of teacher, black board, chalk, books, students, classroom and laboratory and interaction between them.* The teacher uses this environment to create problems for student and then guides them through to experiences leading to desired learning. Here one important point is that all the components except teacher and students of an education system are dependent on technology and has evolved over the development of civilization. With the evolution of computer, software's and internet traditional education tools are going to change without affecting the basic goals of education. We can classify the tools of an education system as follows-

- study material - can be in form of book, can be delivered on line web pages, eLibrary etc.
- Interactivity tools - Black board, white board with chalk, duster, marker etc
- Space – classroom, Lab and associated facility – Infrastructure for operation of educational system.

There is another factor which has to be discussed that is the GER of the higher education of our country is 9.21 in comparison to the primary education 38.89. The Higher education GER of U.P. is 7.57

comparatively low in comparison to GER of India GER and U.P. ranks at 21st position among 35 States and UTs On the other side EMR (educational mortality rate) whereby of 100 children enrolled in class I, not more than 26 reach class X, barely 13 qualify for higher secondary education and only 6 qualify for college education, raises serious concerns with regard to the means adopted in the teaching-learning process and of accountability which is rarely addressed. *For decrease GER and EMR many factors are responsible but two major reasons are that decreasing interest of student in higher education and poor student teacher ratio.* Both problems are solved up to a limit by using New Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) which also provide alternative provisions for access to education without compromising the achievement of comparable goals through different and more appropriate arrangements and means, enable the expansion of the scope, scale and quality of learning. The students are also able to discuss their problems with the subject expert form any where in the world, teachers increase their knowledge so ultimately overall impact is that UP is also able to produce best students in higher education which results in to increase employment and ultimately overall growth and development results in sectors of our state.

This paper is a effort to explain how internet, computer, software and other IT based educational infrastructure are helpful to improve the present traditional educational system.

What are eEducation, online education & eLearning?

In general words we can say that "The use of modern electronic gazettes (Such as computer, digital board, digital pen, educational software, internet etc.) in traditional class room education is known as **eEducation**" where as **online education** is considered as a part of e-education in which by the use of internet a student can studied any time any where and he can also discuss the problems by the expert of subject any where in the world through video conferencing. **eLearning** is basically learning and experiences knowledge through Information and Communication Technology. It is a more learning process rather than teaching. It is to provides educators and learner's podium to express their ideas more easily and naturally, simplify the learning process, provide foundation to interact with each other

वर्तमान समय में शैक्षिक मानदंडों के संविधानुसार परिवर्तन एवं कक्षशिक्षण में आधुनिक तकनीक व सुविधाओं का प्रयोग ;जैसे कम्प्यूटर सॉफ्टवेयर इंटरनेट इत्यादिद्व ई-लर्निंग को बेहतर परिभाषित कर सकता है । ई-लर्निंग का मतलब है एकलव्य का ज्ञान सीखना । जैसे एकलव्य ने केवल गुरु की प्रतिमा स्थापित करके ज्ञान प्राप्त किया था, वैसे ही आधुनिक ई-लर्निंग के द्वारा एक छात्र केवल शिक्षक के पाठ को कहीं भी और कभी भी पढ सकता है ।

e-Learning and online education in U.P. : Present Situation

- In the initial stage in govt and added college and institutions although some private institution and universities are start using the technology in higher education
- Distance Education Program started on Television and Radio some one decade back

Infrastructure for eEducation, online education & eLearning

Basic Tools

- Broad Band internet connection
- Wi-Fi connectivity in the college campus
- Computers and Laptops
- Plasma Screens
- Hi pixel Camera for Video lecture and confessing
- LCD with projection screen
- Website for the connected colleges and institutions and a service provider
- Interactive Pad, Board, Panel and Camera
- Digital pen and communication system

Other tools

- Digital Microscope
- Digital encyclopaedia
- Digital library books and journals
- Smart class rooms
- eLibrary

eLearning software

- Brihaspati (Designed by IIT, Kanpur)
- WebCT (Designed by Univ. of British Columbia)etc.
- Subject related software's
- Virtual dissection software's

Technologies

- eAssessment
- graphic design
- interactive multimedia
- CS-ROM
- Computer labs
- Interactive television education
- Video conferencing
- Audio visual equipments

The Ten Pillars of Successful Technology Integration

- Active support must come from the top
- A non-dictatorial approach is always best
- Every school should have a core of teacher-computerises
- User-friendly technical support must be available, ideally onsite and on demand
- Teacher needs must come first
- Teachers must be given time and freedom to restructure the curriculum around the technology

- An ongoing technology training program must be in place
- Parents and students must be involved in the evolutionary process
- Do not underestimate the ongoing cost of technology-integrated teaching and learning
- Everyone involved—administration, teachers, parents and students—must be committed to the ongoing change in teaching and learning methodologies that will accompany technology integration

Potential Benefit of eLearning in U.P.

- brings a breakthrough in the education system
- teacher and students have a better insight in course
- provide a variety of possibilities to deliver on campus teaching
- change in pedagogical conceptions
- improved media competency of teacher and students
- the enrolment of students' increases
- Enabled far more people to engage in higher education
- the interest of student in the subject increase
- attendance percent increase as the boring teaching replace by interesting method
- outreach goes further
- quality output can also be ensured through improved learning materials which finally help to create a knowledge-based society
- provides an opportunity of high quality education economically, not only to the people in cities but also to those in the rural areas
- The student of rural areas are able to discuss with experts of their field
- Need of subject/topic experts minimise up to a limit in each college
- Student aware with the advancement of their subjects any where in the world
- Traditional education become professional
- Campus placement increases

Expected Result from eEducation System

- Equal educational opportunities and higher education which offers education at quality through the Internet, which offers education at low cost with no limitation in time/space
- Establishment of balanced educational policies between rural and urban area
- Promotion of online contents industry
- Enhanced national competitiveness through knowledge transfer and training of human resources
- Increased computer literacy of the grassroots people through distribution of PCs for e-education
- Better understanding of educational concepts through utilizing ICT as materials supporting class

Partnership for e-Learning

- Developing coherent strategies together through partnership is an urgent need for us to deal successfully in constantly budding knowledge economy
- Partnership for producing tangible results, generating our common interest and promoting strategic interdependence should be promoted
- partnership is a necessity rather than a choice in this era of Globalization

Conclusion

Technology-integrated education is still a dream at all levels of education in U.P. While there are computers in the college, institutions they are mostly used to learn about computers. Rarely are they used as tools for the teaching and learning of other curriculum areas yet. But there is an advantage to India's being behind the times, as long as the leader's in education keep their wits about them. They can skip wire-based technologies altogether. Wi-MAX, the latest generation broadband wireless medium, will be made available everywhere; it's just a matter of time. Computers, too, continue to come down in price. This will enable schools to connect to the internet at speeds that will make internet use, inside and outside the classroom, a viable *adjunct* to chalk and talk and traditional textbook learning—an adjunct, note, not an alternative.

Traditional learning methodologies will continue to have an important place in education. Students who routinely use the computer for learning do so because they have come to value it as a tool for accessing and processing information, for communicating and collaborating, for building a community of learners in which ideas are shared, and for increasing their awareness of the world of knowledge to which they can gain access at the touch of their fingertips. Those who are lucky enough to have the computer as part and parcel of their academic experience would never be without it. *The opportunity to use computers for teaching and learning should not be a privilege. It should be a right, just as it is only right that children should have access to books, pens and paper.* There is a digital divide that separates the haves and have-nots with regard to access to technology. It is only right that the privilege of technology-integrated teaching and learning should be enjoyed by all.

With the convergence of technologies – the computer, CD-ROMs, video and web conferencing, Internet, broadband and television for instance –it is possible for cradle-to-grave learning to become a reality. The digital world today enables children to learn anything from maths to music from teachers across the country and the globe. Students in higher education can attend lectures and tutorials from their homes and community centres; youngsters with profound disabilities have found unprecedented inclusion as universities and colleges have built learning networks opening new opportunities for homemakers just as educational software and digital collections have reinvented museums and libraries.

However, the challenges today are not about technology itself but relate to the role of technology in promoting systemic changes in education and how it can enhance the way we deal with key issues of access and equity, management and efficiency, pedagogy and quality as we prepare citizens for an era of

globalization dominated by technologies related to knowledge, information and communication with its innovative ways of producing, storing, transmitting, accessing and using knowledge and information. Technology only acquires value to the extent that it proves useful for and is beneficial to human purposes. In the context of education, nothing is more important than the need for sound policies and pragmatic strategies relating to investment in technology for education. Knowledge and information is now widely accepted as a new form of wealth, a driving force for the development of individuals, communities and nations. The challenge, therefore, is to enable the population in general to have access to the skills for coping with and the ability to function effectively in this age of information and knowledge, empowering them thereby with improved life-chances and quality of life in a global world.

Suggestions

U.P. Government formulate a core committee which prepare a Master Plan for eEducation, online education & eLearning in U.P. higher education on the basis of their recommendation of committee eEducation and online education started in some Govt., Added and private college, Institutions and Universities as a pilot project for five years and after observation and findings of five years a curriculum decided and eEducation, online education & eLearning started in the U.P. completely. Government of U.P., has identified eEducation as the priority project of the higher education, so our youth become compatible to face the challenges of 21st century and able to put first steps in each sector of the worlds.